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THE EFFECTS OF FARMING IN THE ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF STUDENTS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN FARMING AND NON-FARMING STUDENTS IN QUINAPONDAN NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Food is a basic necessity and agriculture is one of the major sources of our food. To live and to work we all need energy and we get energy through the food that we consume. Agriculture impacts society in many ways, including supporting livelihoods through food, habitat, and jobs, providing raw materials for food and other products also building strong economies through trade. Farming is one of the activities of agriculture that helped humanity to survive and thrive since the beginning of time. According to the vocabulary.com (2023) farming is the act or process of working the ground, planting seeds, and growing edible plants. Also, describing raising animals for milk or meat as farming as well. Farming is a great way to describe the lifestyle and work of people whose jobs are in the agriculture industry. Many people depend on farming and on the production of essential food crops to earn a living. There are different farming activities that is being worked on by farmers, just like planting rice, animal farming, crop yielding, aquaculture and any more. Animal farming/ husbandry according to the Cambridge dictionary (n.d.) is the farming or raising of animals for food such as meat, eggs, and milk. While aquaculture is breeding, raising, and harvesting fish, shellfish, and aquatic plants. Basically, it's farming in water according to the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) (2023). As farming has become the primary source of food as well as livelihood and job to those who are in the agricultural sector. It is also has become the bridging activity made by students who are coming from agricultural families who most likely rely of their farms for income. With such aspect some of the students who are engaging into labor has been performing well but majority of which are struggling when it comes to their academic success. According to the study result of Russell, S. & Elder, G. (1997) children from farm families in rural America show higher academic performance due to high parental involvement and leadership in the local community. Meanwhile in the case study of Punjabi Sikh farm families settled in California by Gibson (1987) immigrant youths from working-class background can often achieve better academic success rather than

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non-immigrants students, especially when receiving all their schooling in their new homeland. Furthermore, students who do their school work in a farm setting significantly improves learning results and experiences, as pupils experience as easier and more effective in a more authentic learning environment according to Smeds, P. et al. (2015). There is also a notable aspect that also should be taken into consideration that could potentially be an aspect of the academic success of a farming student which is their classroom engagement. As defined by Berstein (2022) classroom engagement refers to the degree of attention, curiosity, interest, optimism, and passion that students show when they are learning or being taught, which extends to the level of motivation they have to learn and progress in their education. Also, according to his written article classroom engagement involves three domains, behavioral engagement, emotional engagement and cognitive engagement which were cited in his work according to National Association of Independent Schools (NAIS). Behavioral engagement is focusing on participation in academic, social, and co-curricular activities, while emotional engagement is focusing on the extent and nature of positive and negative reactions to teachers, classmates, academics, and school, and cognitive engagement is focusing on students' level of investment in learning. In the Philippines it could likely be another thing. In a study conducted by Jadia, E. et al. (2023) in a public secondary school in San Jose District, revealing that the academic performance of working students is related to the nature of their work and they use coping-mechanisms. Another study made by Canete (2019), founded out that most of the educational attainment of the farmers' children were elementary level, followed by the secondary level. Nevertheless, there are some farmers' children who were able to finish college and became professionals. These are the things that the researchers would like to uncover for them to see if there could be a possible effect of farming activities/work which is being made by the students to their academic performance.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aims to identify the effects of farming in the academic performance of students, comparing its effects to farming and non-farming students. Specifically, it sought to answer the following problem statements:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their academic performance or General Weighted Average (GWA)?
2. What is the level of engagement of the respondents in farming in terms of:
 - 2.1 Number of hours spent in farming activities; and
 - 2.2 Number of hours spent in studying at home after doing the farming activities.
3. What type of farming activities does the respondents do in terms of:
 - 3.1 Planting rice

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- 3.2 Crop yielding
 - 3.3 Animal farming
 - 3.4 Aquaculture
 4. What is the level of classroom engagement of the respondents in terms of:
 - 4.1 Cognitive engagement
 - 4.2 Behavioral engagement
 - 4.3 Emotional engagement
 5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of engagement of the respondents to their level of classroom engagement?
 6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of engagement of the respondents into farming to their academic performance?
 7. Is there a significant relationship between the farming activities done by the respondents and their academic performance?
 8. Is there a significant difference between the effects of farming to the academic performance of the respondents in both farming and non-farming students?

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study aims to determine the effect of farming in the academic performance of students to both farming and non-farming respondents that will be beneficial to the following individuals or group of people:

Students – they will be encouraged to engage themselves into farming activities and understand its worthwhile learning and performing well in school.

Teachers – for them to develop ways that will help their students who are engaging into farming activities that are struggling in their studies.

Parents – support their children in all means so that they can perform well in school and help them reach their full potential.

Future researchers - The result of this study will be a spring board in opening the different concepts that talks about the same subject matter that leads to further investigations of new researchers.

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SCOPE AND DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study will be focusing on the effects of farming into the academic performance of the students including the investigation of the said effects to both farming and non-farming students. The selected junior high school students will be the respondents for this study due to their direct involvement in learning. The site where the study will be in realization will be at Quinapondan National High School, in the Municipality of Quinapondan of the province of Eastern Samar due its accessibility to the researchers.

DEFINITION OF TERMS

The following words or phrases are given its full definitions as they will come into use in this study:

Animal farming – is the farming or raising of animals for food such as meat, eggs, and milk.

Aquaculture – is breeding, raising, and harvesting fish, shellfish, and aquatic plants. Basically, it's farming in water

Behavioral engagement – is focusing on participation in academic, social, and co-curricular activities.

Cognitive engagement – is focusing on students' level of investment in learning.

Classroom engagement – refers to the degree of attention, curiosity, interest, optimism, and passion that students show when they are learning or being taught, which extends to the level of motivation they have to learn and progress in their education.

Emotional engagement – is focusing on the extent and nature of positive and negative reactions to teachers, classmates, academics, and school.

Farming – is the act or process of working the ground, planting seeds, and growing edible plants. Also, describing raising animals for milk or meat.

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CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter presents the various literatures and studies including articles that supports or talks about the subject matter which is being studied in this paper.

RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

Attending to school regular sometimes is a very hard thing to do specially if you need to engage yourself into working at an early age. In the global perspective working even at an early age is very much common. In a study that took its place in Columbia, study results showed that children who are working regardless of the number of hours they work specially when scheduled in the morning has a negative effect on their academic performance in school (Holgado, D., et al., 2014). Also, according to the study of Emerson, P. et al. (2017) study results revealed that about one quarter to the three-fifths of an average year of learning is lost on the study time of a student due to working. It shows a negative effect in the academic success of students. In another study that focused in the impact of children's work on school performance in the provinces of Pakistan showed that there is a negative relationship between the working hours and school achievements of their children, furthermore, light work along with attending school will not affect the child's academic performance (Salam Lodhi, A., et al., 2014). In the Philippines one prevalent reason why, children engage in early childhood labor is the socio-economic status of their families. In a study conducted in Nueva Ecija having the parents of the respondents involved in the study with the majority of them were working as farmers. Study results revealed that a positive relationship between the families work as farmers to their academic performance because they also engage themselves into working (Raganta, J., et al., 2021). Child labor in the Philippines negatively impacts children's education, health, and recreational activities, with heavy physical work and long working hours leading to higher dropout rates according to Nelson, G., & Quiton, J. (2017). Added by the research study done by Bacolod, M. & Ranjan, P. (2008) child ability and household wealth are the most important determinants of child idleness and child labor, suggesting that policies aiming to reduce child labor and increase child schooling should focus on improving child ability and cognitive development. It is very much a common thing among families who are marginalized to let their children work even at a very young age that eventually slows down their progress in school and worst leads to a large number of drop outs.

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CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study aims to present the connection between the pre-determined variables namely the independent and dependent variables.

INDEPENDENT VARIABLE INTERVENING VARIABLE DEPENDENT VARIABLE

Figure 1: This paradigm shows the link between the two distinct variables which is farming and the academic performance of the respondents having an intervening variable which is classroom engagement.

NULL HYPOTHESIS

HO: There is no significant relationship between the level of engagement in farming of the respondents and their academic performance.

HO1: There is no significant relationship between the type of farming activities done by the respondents to their academic performance.

HO2: There is no significant relationship between the level of engagement of the respondents to their level of classroom engagement

HO3: There is no significant difference between farming and non-farming students when it comes to their academic performance.

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CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the details on how the study will be conducted. This shows and discusses the research design, research locale, respondents of the study, sampling design, research instrument, measurement of variables, data gathering procedure, data analysis and ethical consideration and standards.

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study will utilize quasi-experimental research that involves numerical data collection and statistical analysis. This type of research compares two groups with different circumstances or treatments to find the cause-and-effect links. It draws statistical conclusions from quantitative data (Questionpro, 2023).

RESEARCH LOCALE

This study will be situated in Quinapondan National High School in the municipality of Quinapondan, province of Eastern Samar. A 5th class municipality in the province of Eastern Samar, Philippines. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 14,507 people.

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FIGURE 2: Map of Eastern Samar Wherein the Municipality of Quinapondan is Stipulated

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RESPONDENTS OF THE STUDY

The target respondents of this study will be selected junior high school students of Quinapondan National High School in the municipality of Quinapondan which is an agricultural municipality in the province of Eastern Samar. To qualify to be a respondent of the study, the following criteria was set by the researchers;

Inclusion Criteria:

- A. Officially enrolled in the current SY. 2023-2024.
- B. A Junior High School student of Quinapondan National High School.
- C. Must be willing to be a respondent of this study.

SAMPLING DESIGN

A simple random sampling technique will be utilized in this study on the determination of the target respondents. Simple random sampling is a randomly selected subset of a population. In this sampling method, each member of the population has an exactly equal chance of being selected. This method is the most straightforward of all the probability sampling methods, since it only involves a single random selection and requires little advance knowledge about the population. This also secures the eradication of bias among the selection of the target respondents.

SAMPLE SIZE

In identifying the total number of respondents from coming from the total population. The Slovin's formula will be used in the calculation of the actual total number of respondents for this study with an acceptable margin of error. The formula is calculated as:

Slovin's formula: Whereas,

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

n = Number of respondents

N = Total Population

e = Margin of error

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RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

To acquire the data that should be used in this study, a researcher modified questionnaire will be employed. But with such revisions made by the researchers to the instrument it is still adopted from the study of Tancenco, N. & Garcia, C. entitled "Academic performance and level of life support skills among working students in Naval State University". To ensure that the appropriate data will be accumulated from the respondents of this study a minor revision to the instrument was made. To ensure the reliability of the researcher modified instrument a pilot testing will be done with the use of the Cronbach's Alpha as the statistical tool of analysis.

DATA GATHERING PROCEDURE

Right before the actual distribution of the data gathering instrument of this study, appropriate letter of communication and approval will be handed over to all concerned head of offices. Starting from the office the Schools Division Superintendent of the Eastern Samar Division, Department of Education. Right after the approval of the letter of communication coming from the office of the head of Eastern Samar Division with the intent to conduct a data gathering procedure in the identified school of study, the next action to be made will be hand over of another letter of communication, it will be to the Principal or School head of Quinapondan National High School. Lastly upon the approval of the said letter, the approval of the class adviser will be secured. The data gathering procedure will commence but before it starts the researchers will inform the respondents about how valuable the informations to be acquired from them, and then finally, the distribution of the questionnaire to the target respondents will be made. Right after the collection of the questionnaires all of the data will be consolidated, tabulated and analyzed using the appropriate statistical tools.

MEASUREMENT OF VARIABLES

To accurately measure the set of data that will be accumulated from the participants appropriate measurement of variables and measure of central tendency must be identified.

Variables	Measurement Of Variables	Measures Of Central Tendency
General Weighted Average	Numerical	Mean
Number of hours working and studying	Numerical	Median

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Type of Farming activity	Nominal	Frequency and percentage
Classroom engagement	Ordinal	Frequency and percentage

DATA ANALYSIS

In this study collected set of data will be quantitatively assessed using the following tests. For the assessment of the general weighted average the mean score will be calculated, while for the number of hours working and studying will be the median. Another thing is that frequency and percentage will be solved, according to Jove (2023) A percentage frequency distribution, in general, is a display of data that indicates the percentage of observations for each data point or grouping of data points. It is a commonly used method for expressing the relative frequency of survey responses and other data. The percentage frequency distributions are often displayed as bar graphs, pie charts, or tables. To test the difference between the effect of farming in the academic performance of students in both farming and non-farming learner a T-test statistical analysis will be employed. According to Bevans (2023) a t-test is a statistical test that is used to compare the means of two groups. It is often used in hypothesis testing to determine whether a process or treatment actually has an effect on the population of interest, or whether two groups are different from one another. Also, the use of Spearman's correlation for data that follow curvilinear, monotonic relationships and for ordinal data. Statisticians also refer to Spearman's rank order correlation coefficient as Spearman's ρ (rho).

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CHAPTER IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the different results that were founded out through the data gathering procedure as well as the discussion of the said collected set of data.

RESULTS

General Weighted Average

The first table presents the relative frequency and percentage of the data that were gathered with regards to the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their academic performance which is measured through their general weighted average. Based from the result of the data analysis, 19 or 37.3% of the respondents has a general weighted average of 80-85 and 26 or 51.0% of the respondents has a grade of 86-90 in which it was the largest concentration of grades. While there were only 6 or 11.8% of the respondents who have a grade of 91-95.

Table 1: General Weighted Average

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
GWA		
80-85	19	37.3 %
86-90	26	51.0 %
91-95	6	11.8 %

Farming and Non-Farming Students

The second table shows the frequency and percentage of the number of students who are involved in farming and those students who are not involved to the activity. There were 40 or 78.4% of the respondents who are involved in farming and 11 or 21.6% of the remaining respondents who are not involved in farming.

Table 2: Farming and Non-Farming Students

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
FARMING AND NON-FARMING STUDENTS		
Farming	40	78.4 %

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Non-Farming	11	21.6 %
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Time Spent in Farming Activities and Time Spent in Studying

The third table presents the number of hours spent by students who are engaged in farming. The highest number of hours spent by the respondents in doing farming activities is 1-2 hours a day having 30 or 58.8 percent of the total number of respondents. Next is 3-4 hours per day having a total number of 16 or 31.4 percent of the respondents. While, 5-6 hours has a frequency of 2 which is 3.9 percent and for 7-8 hours a day has 3 or 5.9% of the remaining total number of participants. On the other hand, time spent by the respondents after doing farm work as well as those who are not engaged in farming is also presented. There are 19 or 37.3% of the respondents are spending 10-20 mins a day on studying after doing farm work. Also, there are 14 or 27.5% of the respondents who are studying after doing farm work for at least 30-40 minutes a day. While, for the 50-60 minutes and 1-1 ½ hours a day there are 3 or 5.9% respectively. There is only 1 or 2.0% of the participants studies after farm work for 1 ½ to 2 hours per day. Finally, is that of the students who are not involved in farming spending time of more than 2 hours/day having 11 or 21.6% of the total number of respondents.

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
TIME SPENT IN FARMING		
1-2 Hours/Day	24	47.1 %
3-4 Hours/Day	12	23.5 %
5-6 Hours/Day	1	3.9 %
7-8 Hours/Day	3	5.9 %
Zero Hours	11	21.6%
TIME SPENT IN STUDYING AFTER DOING FARM WORK		
10-20 Mins/Day	19	37.3 %
30-40 Mins/Day	14	27.5 %
50-60 Mins/Day	3	5.9 %
1-1:30 Hours/Day	3	5.9 %
1:30-2 Hours/Day	1	2.0 %

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2 Hours and Above	11	21.6 %
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Table 3: Time Spent in Farming Activities and Time Spent in Studying

Type of Farming Activity

The fourth table shows the type of farming activity that the respondents were into. Based on the result of the data analysis, planting rice and animal farming both have a frequency of 16 which is 31.4 percent of the total number of respondents. While, there are 11 or 21.5 % of the respondents who are not into farming. Crop yielding has a frequency of 7 or 13.7% which shows the number of students involved to this farming activity. There is only 1 or 2.0 percent from the total number of respondents is into aquaculture.

Table 4: Type of Farming Activity

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
FARMING ACTIVITY		
Planting Rice	16	31.4
Crop Yeilding	7	13.7
Animal Farming	16	31.4
Aquaculture	1	2.0
None	11	21.5

Effect of Farming

The fifth table presents the level of farming to the students in terms of their cognitive, behavioral and emotional domains. The data results shows that there are 3 indicators that are interpreted as neutral which are indicators 2,3 and 9, meaning to the respondents farming has an effect or has no effect in terms of their cognitive, behavioral and emotional domains. While, indicators number 1,4,5,6,7,8,10,11,12 and 13 were interpreted as effective. This refers to a certain level or degree of effect to the respondents, their care about the subject, feel motivated or excited to learn, and take ownership of their own learning. On the other hand, indicators 14 and 15 are interpreted as Highly Effective, this means the extent to which students show attention, curiosity, optimism and interest in the material that they are being taught is affected highly by farming. Students' cognitive investment in their learning, including participating and committing to their studies is also high. In the case study of Punjabi Sikh farm families settled in California by Gibson (1987) immigrant youths from working-class background can often achieve better academic success rather than non-

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immigrants students, especially when receiving all their schooling in their new homeland. Furthermore, students who do their schoolwork in a farm setting significantly improves learning results and experiences, as pupils experience as easier and more effective in a more authentic learning environment according to Smeds, P. et al. (2015).

INDICATORS	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
Staying up on the readings.	3.13	Effective
Showing persistence on more challenging tasks.	2.84	Neutral
Demonstrating appropriate efforts for tasks.	2.90	Neutral
Self-motivated in doing tasks.	3.23	Effective
Trying to understand things that were learnt at school.	3.54	Effective
Finding ways to make the course material relevant to my life.	3.11	Effective
Has good attendance.	3.05	Effective
Participates in class discussions actively.	3.01	Effective
Referred for out of class disciplinary procedures.	2.80	Neutral

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Respectful to peers and teachers.	3.56	Effective
Helping fellow students.	3.29	Effective
Interested in school.	4.00	Effective
Get along with peers.	3.64	Effective
Cares about grades.	4.19	Highly Effective
Enjoys learning new things in class.	4.29	Highly Effective
GRAND MEAN	3.38	EFFECTIVE

Table 5: Effect of Farming
Correlation

Time Spent in Farming Activities vs. Academic Performance

This following tables shows the result about the relative connection of the different variables that were pre-determined by the researchers. The sixth table presents the connection of the time spent by the students in farming activities to their level of classroom engagement. The result shows that there is a weak positive correlation between the two pre-determined variable having a correlation coefficient value of .005 which means that the time spent by the respondents in farming has a little effect on their academic performance and based on the level of significance with a p-value result of .971 which is interpreted as not significant, the null hypothesis of this study was failed to be accepted. As supported by a study that has focused on the impact of children's work on school performance in the provinces of Pakistan showed that there is a negative relationship between the working hours and school achievements of their children, furthermore, light work along with attending school will not affect the child's academic performance (*Salam Lodhi, A., et al., 2014*).

Indicators	Correlation	Level of Significance	Decision
	Measure Interpretation	p-value Interpretation	

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Time Spent in Farming Activities vs.					
Academic Performance	.005	Weak positive Correlation	.971	Not Significant	Accept Null Hypothesis

Table 6: Time Spent in Farming Activities vs. Academic Performance

Time Spent in Studying after Doing Farming Activities vs. Academic Performance

The seventh table presents the connection between the time spent by the respondents in studying after doing some farming activities and their Academic Performance. Base on the result of the analysis of data the correlation coefficient value is -.110 which is interpreted as weak negative correlation, meaning the regardless of the number of hours spent by the respondents in studying after doing some farming activities has nothing to do with their Academic Performance. With the p-value result of .442 which is interpreted as not significant it is safe to say that the null hypothesis was failed to be accepted. According to the study of Emerson, P. et al. (2017) study results revealed that about one quarter to the three-fifths of an average year of learning is lost on the study time of a student due to working. It shows a negative effect in the academic success of students.

Table 7: Time Spent in Studying after Doing Farming Activities vs. Academic Performance

Indicators	Correlation		Level of Significance		Decision
	Measure	Interpretation	p-value	Interpretation	
Time Spent in studying after doing Farming Activities vs.					
Academic Performance	-.015	Weak Negative Correlation	.917	Not Significant	Accept Null Hypothesis

Type of Farming Activity vs. Academic Performance

The eight table shows the relationship between the type of farming activity done by the respondents and their Academic Performance. The result presents that there is a weak positive correlation between the two variables with a correlation coefficient value of .087 meaning that the type of farming activity that the students are doing has a little effect when it comes to their Academic Performance. Furthermore, the level of significance of the said variables has a p-value of .554 which is not significant so therefore the null hypothesis was failed to be accepted. As

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supported by a study result that revealed that a positive relationship between the families work as farmers has something to do to their academic performance because they also engage themselves into working (Raganta, J., et al., 2021).

Table 8: Type of Farming Activity vs. Academic Performance

Indicators	Correlation		Level of Significance		Decision
	Measure	Interpretation	p-value	Interpretation	
Type of Farming Activity vs. Level of Classroom Engagement	.087	Weak positive Correlation	.554	Not Significant	Accept Null Hypothesis

Difference between the effect of farming in the academic performance of farming and non-farming students.

In this final table, a difference in both farming and non-farming students is measured. In this case the analysis result shows that there is a negative relationship between farming and the academic performance of farming and non-farming students with a value of 21.795^a with a likelihood of 24.21 which is low alongside with a negative linear association. Such result means that whether a student is engaged in farming or not has nothing to do with their academic performance. Farming has become the bridging activity made by students who are coming from agricultural families who most likely rely on their farms for income. With such aspect some of the students who are engaging into labor have been performing well but majority of which are struggling when it comes to their academic success according to the study result of Russell, S. & Elder, G. (1997). Also, the study result shows that there is a no significant difference between a farming and a non-farming students' academic performance with a level of significance of .591 meaning regardless of the activity made by a student it can or it cannot affect their academic performance that is why the null hypothesis was accepted. *Study results revealed that a positive relationship between the families work as farmers to their academic performance because they also engage themselves into working (Raganta, J., et al., 2021).* Child labor in the Philippines negatively impacts children's education, health, and recreational activities, with heavy physical work and long working hours leading to higher dropout rates according to Nelson, G., & Quizon, J. (2017).

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Table 9: Difference between the effect of farming in the academic performance of farming and non-farming students.

Indicators	Value	Df	Interpretation	Decision
Farming and Non-Farming students vs. Academic Performance	21.795 ^a	24	Not Significant	Accept Null Hypothesis

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CHAPTER V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of the study, conclusions derived from the major outcomes of the study and recommendation in the light of the findings of the conclusion.

SUMMARY

As results were revealed based on the different statistical analysis a summary is drawn as presented in the following manner. This study aims to identify the effects of farming in the academic performance of students, comparing its effects to farming and non-farming students. Specifically, it sought to answer the following problem statements. (1) What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their academic performance or General Weighted Average (GWA)? (2) What is the level of engagement of the respondents in farming in terms of: Number of hours spent in farming activities; and Number of hours spent in studying at home after doing the farming activities. (3) What type of farming activities does the respondents do in terms of: Planting rice, Crop yielding, Animal farming, and Aquaculture. (4) What is the level of effect of farming to the respondents in terms of their: Cognitive Domain, Behavioral Domain, and Emotional Domain. (5) Is there a significant relationship between the level of engagement to farming of the respondents to their level of classroom engagement? (6) Is there a significant relationship between the level of engagement of the respondents into farming to their academic performance? (7) Is there a significant relationship between the farming activities done by the respondents and their academic performance? (8) Is there a significant difference between the effects of farming to the academic performance of the respondents in both farming and non-farming students? With such aim which was guided out by the different problem statement through the data gathering procedure that was followed by the data analysis the following results were drawn. With regards to the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their academic performance which is measured through their general weighted average. Based on the result of the data analysis, 19 or 37.3% of the respondents has a general weighted average of 80-85 which is 26 in total or 51.0% of the respondents has a grade of 86-90 in which it was the largest concentration of grades. While there were only 6 or 11.8% of the respondents who have a grade of 91-95. Second is students who are involved in farming and those students who are not involved to the activity. There were 40 or 78.4% of the respondents who are involved in farming and 11 or 21.6% of the remaining respondents who are not involved in farming. For the next problem statement, the highest number of hours spent by the respondents in doing farming activities is 1-2 hours a day having 30 or 58.8 percent of the total number of respondents. Next is 3-4 hours per day having a total number of 16 or 31.4 percent of the respondents. While, 5-6 hours has a frequency of 2 which is 3.9 percent and for 7-8 hours a day has 3 or 5.9% of the remaining total number of participants. On the other hand, time spent by the respondents after doing farm work as well as those

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who are not engaged in farming is also presented. There are 19 or 37.3% of the respondents are spending 10-20 mins a day on studying after doing farm work. Also, there are 14 or 27.5% of the respondents who are studying after doing farm work for at least 30-40 minutes a day. While, for the 50-60 minutes and 1-1 ½ hours a day there are 3 or 5.9% respectively. There is only 1 or 2.0% of the participants studies after farm work for 1 ½ to 2 hours per day. Finally, is that of the students who are not involved in farming spending time of more than 2 hours/day having 11 or 21.6% of the total number of respondents. For the third problem statement based on the result of the data analysis, planting rice and animal farming both have a frequency of 16 which is 31.4 percent of the total number of respondents. While there are 11 or 21.5 % of the respondents who are not into farming. Crop yielding has a frequency of 7 or 13.7% which shows the number of students involved to this farming activity. There is only 1 or 2.0 percent from the total number of respondents is into aquaculture. Also, the data results shows that there are 3 indicators that are interpreted as neutral which are indicators 2,3 and 9, meaning to the respondents farming has an effect or has no effect in terms of their cognitive, behavioral and emotional domains. While, indicators number 1,4,5,6,7,8,10,11,12 and 13 were interpreted as effective. This refers to a certain level or degree of effect to the respondents, their care about the subject, feel motivated or excited to learn, and take ownership of their own learning. On the other hand, indicators 14 and 15 are interpreted as Highly Effective, this means the extent to which students show attention, curiosity, optimism and interest in the material that they are being taught is affected highly by farming. Students' cognitive investment in their learning, including participating and committing to their studies is also high. While for the correlation of the effect of farming to the academic performance of the respondents the following results were revealed, there is a weak positive correlation between the two pre-determined variable having a correlation coefficient value of .005 which means that the time spent by the respondents in farming has a little effect on their academic performance and based on the level of significance with a p-value result of .971 which is interpreted as not significant, the null hypothesis of this study was failed to be accepted. The result of the analysis of data the correlation coefficient value is -.110 which is interpreted as weak negative correlation, meaning the regardless of the number of hours spent by the respondents in studying after doing some farming activities has nothing to do with their Academic Performance. With the p-value result of .442 which is interpreted as not significant it is safe to say that the null hypothesis was failed to be accepted. The result presents that there is a weak positive correlation between the two variables with a correlation coefficient value of .087 meaning that the type of farming activity that the students are doing has a little effect when it comes to their Academic Performance. Furthermore, the level of significance of the said variables has a p-value of .554 which is not significant so therefore the null hypothesis was failed to be accepted. Analysis result shows that there is a negative relationship between farming and the academic performance of farming and non-farming students with a value of 21.795^a with a likelihood of 24.21 which is low alongside with a negative linear association. Such result means that whether a student is engaged in farming or not has nothing to do with their academic performance.

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CONCLUSION

Based on the yield of this study the following conclusions were made by the researchers:

- A. In terms of the academic performance of the students, farming has a minor effect on it based on the results founded out by this study. Majority of the respondents has a general weighted average of 86-90 which is 26 in total or 51.0%, followed by 19 or 37.3% of the respondents has a general weighted average of 80-85 and 6 or 11.8% of the respondents who have a grade of 91-95.
- B. The highest number of hours spent by the respondents in doing farming activities is 1-2 hours a day having 30 or 58.8 percent of the total number of respondents. Next is 3-4 hours per day having a total number of 16 or 31.4 percent of the respondents. While, 5-6 hours has a frequency of 2 which is 3.9 percent and for 7-8 hours a day has 3 or 5.9% of the remaining total number of participants. On the other hand, time spent by the respondents after doing farm work as well as those who are not engaged in farming is also presented. There are 19 or 37.3% of the respondents are spending 10-20 mins a day on studying after doing farm work. Also, there are 14 or 27.5% of the respondents who are studying after doing farm work for at least 30-40 minutes a day. While, for the 50-60 minutes and 1-1 ½ hours a day there are 3 or 5.9% respectively. There is only 1 or 2.0% of the participants studies after farm work for 1 ½ to 2 hours per day. Finally, is that of the students who are not involved in farming spending time of more than 2 hours/day having 11 or 21.6% of the total number of respondents.
- C. Farming influences students with regards to their cognitive, behavioral and emotional domains. As the study results revealed that based on the different indicators farming has an effect the students' performance.
- D. Based on the result of the data analysis, planting rice and animal farming both have a frequency of 16 which is 31.4 percent of the total number of respondents. While there are 11 or 21.5 % of the respondents who are not into farming. Crop yielding has a frequency of 7 or 13.7% which shows the number of students involved to this farming activity. There is only 1 or 2.0 percent from the total number of respondents is into aquaculture.
- E. Time spent on farming and the respondents time in studying after doing farm work has a minor effect in their academic performance as they can still excel in studying and in their social domain.
- F. Regardless of the type of farming activity a student engages into has a little effect on their academic performance based on the study result and also as support by the different studies that supports this claim.
- G. To both farming and non-farming students the effect of farming is low as they can both perform well in their studies. As the study results revealed that either both students who are involved in doing farming activities and those who were not involved has the potential to excel in class.

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RECOMMENDATION

After a thorough investigation and analysis of the information's which were accumulated, the following recommendation were made by the researchers.

- A. Students must put more emphasis into studying while still managing to do their tasks by being mentally, physically and emotionally active.
- B. Parents should always put into consideration the welfare of their children by letting them study for a much longer time and lesser time for helping in doing farming activities.
- C. Teachers should be more considerable when it comes to the students who are involved in doing farming activities as they are physically exhausted and mentally unready when coming to school. Putting on an extra effort to teach them so that they can perform well in class.
- D. Curriculum designers and administrators should be able to create tasks that can easily be done but can holistically mold a child into a more productive individual not just only cognitively but also physically and emotionally.
- E. The community must become more supportive to their constituents specially the younger generation by conducting activities that can develop their cognitive, psycho-motor and affective skills.
- F. The local government must give an ample support to farming families for them to be able to let their children focus on studying and refrain from doing heavy farm work.
- G. The national government must re-enforce their projects and activities that are meant to help the poor Filipino farmers. They must strengthen their way of support so that the children of farming families will not engage into extraneous farming activities but instead be more focused on learning and molding themselves into becoming a more holistic type of individual.

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**THE EFFECTS OF FARMING IN THE ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF STUDENTS: A
COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN FARMING AND NON-FARMING STUDENTS IN
QUINAPONDAN NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL
QUESTIONNAIRE**

PART I: DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

DIRECTION: Please answer the following items based on your own understanding.
Write the needed information's asked for each item.

- A. General Weighted Average: _____
B. Farming: _____ Non-Farming: _____

PART II: LEVEL OF ENGAGEMENT TO FARMING IN TERMS OF TIME SPENT

A. TIME SPENT IN FARM ACTIVITIES

- 1-2 HOURS/DAY
 3-4 HOURS/DAY
 5-6 HOURS/DAY
 7-8 HOURS/DAY
 9-10 HOURS/DAY

B. TIME SPENT STUDYING AFTER DOING FARM ACTIVITIES

- 10-20 MINS/DAY
 30-40 MINS/DAY
 50-60 MINS/DAY
 1-1:30 HOURS/DAY
 1:30-2 HOURS/DAY

PART III: TYPE OF FARMING ACTIVITY

- PLANTING RICE
 CROP YEILDING
 ANIMAL FARMING
 AQUACULTURE

PART IV: EFFECTS OF FARMING

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INDICATORS	HIGHLY NO EFFECT (1)	NO EFFECT (2)	NEUTRAL (3)	EFFECTIVE (4)	HIGHLY EFFECTIVE (5)
COGNITIVE DOMAIN					
Staying up on the readings.					
Showing persistence on more challenging tasks.					
Demonstrating appropriate efforts for tasks.					
Self-motivated in doing tasks.					
Trying to understand things that were learnt at school.					
BEHAVIORAL DOMAIN					
Finding ways to make the course material relevant to my life.					
Has good attendance.					
Participates in class					

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discussions actively.					
Referred for out of class disciplinary procedures.					
Respectful to peers and teachers.					
EMOTIONAL DOMAIN					
Helping fellow students.					
Interested in school.					
Get along with peers.					
Cares about grades.					
Enjoys learning new things in class.					

**"Academic performance and level of life support skills among working students in Naval State University" & Hart, S. et al. 2011 "The Student Engagement in Schools Questionnaire (SESQ) and the Teacher Engagement Report Form-New (TERF-N): Examining the Preliminary Evidence" **

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